

Ground layer adaptive optics wavefront error budget for MOSAIC

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ABSTRACT

The MOSAIC wide field spectrograph will benefit from ground layer adaptive optics (GLAO) correction using the ELT's adaptive M4 mirror, 4 laser guide stars and 4-5 natural guide stars. The residual wavefront error is dominated by the combination of the turbulence profile, the conjugation height of M4 (621 metres) and the size of the corrected field. Many of the less significant error sources, including static/slowly-varying field-dependent aberrations, would be considered to be very large in most AO systems. The relevant performance metric is the enclosed energy (EE) within an aperture approximately 600 mas or 150 mas in diameter, depending on the observing mode.

Constructing a wavefront error budget for MOSAIC is a different problem to that for an AO system in the high-Strehl regime. The relationship between the residual wavefront error and EE depends strongly on the spatial frequency of the wavefront errors, not just their amplitude. For example, a spherical aberration term reduces the EE substantially more than a defocus term with the same RMS WFE. The RMS WFE is therefore not a relevant metric.

We describe the methods used to model the instrument EE and converge towards an error budget. These involve a three stage PSF generation process: (i) Monte Carlo simulation of the AO-corrected PSF, (ii) addition of static aberrations via filtering of the OTF, and (iii) incorporation of image motion via convolution with a 2D Gaussian function. We present the current state of the error budget and the expected instrument EE with the main error sources accounted for.

Keywords: MOSAIC, GLAO, error budget

1. INTRODUCTION

MOSAIC is a fibre-fed spectrograph for ELT with a 7.8 arcmin diameter field of view [1]. It will include ground layer adaptive optics (GLAO) correction using the ELT's adaptive M4 mirror, 4 laser guide stars, and 4-5 natural guide stars to increase the light captured by the fibres [2].

Constructing a wavefront error budget for MOSAIC is a rather different problem to that for an AO system in the high-Strehl regime. The GLAO residual wavefront error is dominated by the combination of the turbulence profile, the conjugation height of M4 (621 metres) and the size of the corrected field. These terms alone can sum to 900 nm RMS. Many of the less significant error sources, including static/slowly-varying field-dependent aberrations due to opto-mechanical distortions of the telescope, would be considered to be very large in most AO systems.

Table 1. MOSAIC key parameters.

Parameter	Value
Number of targets	285 MOS targets + 8 mini-IFUs
Technical FoV	\varnothing 7.8 arcmin
Wavelength range	0.39 – 1.8 μm
Spectral resolution	LR > 4000, HR > 18000
IFU	2.5" with 150 mas spaxels
MOS aperture	VIS: 0.7", NIR: 0.6"

The key performance metric is the enclosed energy (EE) within an aperture 600 mas or 150 mas in diameter, depending on the observing mode. The relationship between the residual wavefront error and EE depends strongly on the spatial frequency of the wavefront errors, not just their amplitude. As shown in figure 1, a spherical aberration term (Z11) reduces the EE several times as much as a defocus term (Z4) with the same RMS WFE. Simply summing RMS WFE error terms in quadrature is therefore not sufficient as a means of constructing an error budget.

Figure 1. Reduction in GLAO-corrected EE resulting from a static aberration consisting of a single Zernike mode (following Noll’s numbering scheme). For reference, the GLAO residual error is typically around 900nm.

2. MOSAIC PSF SIMULATION

Instrument PSFs are generated in a three-stage process. The first step is a more traditional AO simulation, and additional instrumental error sources are then added to the PSFs in two (far less computationally demanding) post-processing steps. This approach allows for rapid recomputation of the EE when the additional terms are adjusted.

1. Monte Carlo GLAO simulation

GLAO-corrected PSFs are simulated using the “Angus” Monte Carlo AO simulation code (contact: TB). Numerous error sources can be included but performance is dominated by (i) conjugation of the adaptive M4 mirror to 621 metres, (ii) optimization of the reconstructor over a 5x5 arcmin field. Figure 2 shows an example of the field geometry.

2. Static aberrations

Static aberrations are added to the PSFs via filtering of the optical transfer function (OTF) [3]. This method is only valid provided the Monte Carlo PSF has converged sufficiently well (and does not already include a static aberration). Errors added include field-varying ELT aberrations and focus sensing errors (which are dominated by telescope vibrations). Slowly-varying aberrations can also be included, if needed, by summing a series of PSFs with different static aberrations.

3. Gaussian convolution

The PSF is convolved with a 2-dimensional Gaussian probability density function to account for image motion during the instrument exposure. Multiple image motion terms are combined here, including common motion (e.g. vibration) and a radially varying field rotation term.

Figure 2. Field positions used in a MOSAIC GLAO simulation. The outer broken line shows the edge of the ELT field.

Figure 3. Example simulated PSFs. (i) GLAO-only, (ii) with static aberrations incorporated via OTF filtering and (iii) after Gaussian convolution.

3. POSITIONING ERROR

In addition to optimizing the PSF, accurate positioning of the fibres is essential to maximizing the energy delivered to the spectrographs. Absolute positioning of the fibres in open loop is required during target acquisition. The requirement is an absolute EE loss of no more than 2.5% due to misalignment between the source and the aperture. The positioning accuracy needed to meet this requirement is not the same for all observing modes and wavelengths, as shown in figures 4 and 5.

Figure 4. MOS and IFU apertures (to scale).

Figure 5. Example of absolute EE losses as a function of aperture positioning error in the focal plane. Median conditions, zenith angle 45° .

4. CONCLUSIONS

We have described the challenges in constructing a wavefront error budget for MOSAIC, where the residual errors are large and the performance metrics depend on the spatial frequencies as well as the amplitude of aberrations. We have presented an approach that involves computing PSFs in several stages, allowing adjustments to error terms to be made and the predicted performance to be recomputed without re-running complete end-to-end simulations.

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